

The river floodplain area of Uttar Pradesh State occupies nearly 1.5 million ha; main rivers are the Ganga, Yamuna, Sarda, Gomti, Saryu, and Gandak. The Gomti accounts for 0.20 million ha. Adopting cropping sequences of rice - mustard or rice - wheat could significantly improve its agriculture. □

Rice cultivation practices in a Negrito foraging society in northeastern Luzon, Philippines

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The Casiguran Agta, a Negrito population in northeastern Luzon, Philippines, are nomadic hunters and gatherers. Many households, however, also make swiddens (slash-and-burn fields), and a few cultivate wet rice paddies. In 1984, 609 Agta were living in a 700-m² rainforest area in northern Aurora Province. Rainfall averages 3,448 mm/yr.

For 19 mo in 1983-84, we studied Agta cultivation practices by measuring and recording crop data and interviewing field owners. It was a good year, with no significant crop damage from insects or weather. Twenty-two percent of households planted crops, sharing harvests with others. They cultivated 43 swiddens and 5 irrigated rice paddies.

The Agta spend little time in agriculture. Overall, men and women gave 6% of their days to this task (range 0-36%). Total cropped area was 8.6 ha, 91% in rice, only 141 m² per capita. Rice cropping was 128 m² per capita. Mean swidden size was 0.14 ha (s.d.: 0.11 ha), mean paddy size was 0.53 ha.

Total annual rough rice production was 9.1 t, 4.7 t from swiddens and 4.4 t from paddies, enough to feed the population for only 15 d. Mean rough rice yield from swiddens was 0.9 t/ha (n=17). One paddy yielded 1.7 t/ha.

The Agta planted 10 different rice varieties in the swiddens. They grew 47 cultivars of all crops in swiddens, averaging 7.5 cultivars/ swidden, including rice (s.d.: 6.3, range: 1-27).

To our knowledge, the Agta have the smallest swiddens of any cultural group in SE Asia (1/7 ha), the fewest rice varieties/ swidden (1.5), and the fewest cultivars/swidden (7.5). Though they eat rice at 92% of their meals, only 5% of

the rice they eat comes from their own fields. They secure most of it by trading minor forest products and through casual wage labor for outsiders. The Agta cultivate rice mainly as a hobby and for prestige, rather than to produce food. They are not farmers, and since Spanish records show they were making swiddens in the 1700s, they are not evolving from foraging to farming. □

Cassava varieties for 5-mo summer rice fallow in Kerala

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Extensive rice areas in Kerala have a pattern of two rice crops—one medium-duration rice for rainy (May-Aug) season and one long-duration for dry season (Aug-Dec)—followed by a 5-mo summer fallow. We tested five cassava

varieties for summer fallow in a replicated yield trial during summer 1987. We used 75- × 75-cm spacing, 50-50-50 kg NPK/ ha, a basal application of cattle manure at 12.5 t/ ha, and irrigation every 2 wk.

Varieties Co 2 (recently released from Tamil Nadu) and M4 (already popular in Kerala for a 9-10 mo season) are suited to the 5-mo summer rice fallow season under Kerala conditions (see table). □

Performance of 5 cassava varieties in the 5-mo summer rice fallow season. Pattambi, Kerala, 1987.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Tuber yield (t/ha)	Tuber characteristics		
			Length (cm)	Girth (cm)	Softening on cooking
Co 2	102	12.6	22	12	Very good
M4	123	11.6	22	11	Very good
Malavella	117	10.0	26	12	Very good
12/77	141	9.1	25	11	Good
11/76	124	10.3	24	12	Good
LSD (P = 0.05)	—	2.0	—	—	—

Data management and computer modeling

Modeling feeding rates of rice leaffolder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* on different plant stages

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The rice LF damages plants by feeding on the leaves, removing patches of photosynthetic tissue. Daily leaf area

consumed can be measured by exposing larvae of known age to susceptible rice. The cumulative consumption by a larva at age *t* represents the total leaf consumption from hatching to that age.

The first three instars fed little. More than 90% of feeding was done by the 4th and 5th instars age 11-19 d after hatching. The data fit an exponential model extremely well. The model is

$$C_t = e^{\beta t} - 1.0$$